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SUSTAINABLE FARMING FUTURES: THE ECONOMIC NEED OF CLIMATE CHANGE PROGRAM IN UZBEKISTAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Uzbekistan is known as one of the main fruit and vegetable producers among the commonwealth of independent states (Hasanov et al., 2014). In addition, almost half of the population lives in rural areas (Statistics Agency data, 2023). Therefore, agricultural sector is one of the most important sector in Uzbekistan: almost 24% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) accounted for agricultural in 2023 (Statistics Agency data, 2023) and over 25% of employed population work in the sector (Statistics Agency data, 2023). Over the last few years, the market size of agricultural products has seen annual growth and this is improving food security of the country. In order to have higher profit from vegetable and fruit farms, farmers are working with exact plans to develop export markets for these products (Uzbekistan – Agricultural Sectors, 2021). However, there are some challenges in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan which are waiting for possible solutions. Environmental shortcomings are known as the most crucial ones that will be discussed in this policy brief. The brief will also illustrate ongoing activities making sustainable agriculture and will recommend policy options to contribute to successful greening agenda.

KEY CHALLENGES

- **Capacity Building and Awareness Raising:** Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) identified by UNESCO is known as a systematic approach of analyzing and mitigating the various factors that contribute to disaster occurrences. Thus, the goal of DRR training is to equip individuals with the knowledge and skills to comprehend the risks posed by disasters and to implement strategies aimed at mitigating these risks. Given the potential correlation, albeit not yet confirmed causally, between DRR training and people's incomes, particularly in agriculture, water management, and environmental sectors, enhancing risk resilience among farming communities becomes crucial. Study by Global Green Growth in 2022 shows despite a strong willingness among respondents to expand their farming endeavors, only 30% reported having undergone DRR training, indicating an unmet demand that in some part of Uzbekistan. Considering these factors, alongside the worsening farming conditions due to dwindling natural

resources in the region, it is highly recommended to prioritize the provision of risk resilience capacity development for farmers in the project area. This targeted intervention would address both the existing demand and the pressing need to bolster farming resilience in the face of environmental challenges.

- **Greenhouse Gas Emissions of agriculture:** Investigations done by USAID in 2014 finds that Uzbekistan’s total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions amounted to 214.70 million metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (MtCO₂e), which represented approximately 0.44 percent of global GHG emissions. Notably, the energy sector emerged as the primary contributor to Uzbekistan’s GHG emissions, accounting for 89.4 percent of the total emissions. Agriculture followed, contributing 13.1 percent, while industrial processes and waste sectors contributed 2.7 percent and 2.4 percent, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1: GHG Emissions by sector in Uzbekistan

Source: USAID Factsheet

Interestingly, Uzbekistan’s land-use change and forestry (LUCF) sector acted as a net carbon sink in 2014 (Greenhouse gas emissions factsheet: Uzbekistan, 2014). This means that it absorbed 16.40 MtCO₂e more than it emitted during the same period. This finding underscores the potential role of land management practices in mitigating GHG emissions and highlights the importance of sustainable land-use strategies in Uzbekistan’s overall climate change mitigation efforts. In accordance with its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC), Uzbekistan has set a carbon intensity target, committing to reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions per unit of GDP by 10% by the year 2030 compared to 2010 levels (UNDP climate promise, 2021). This target aims to facilitate economic development while simultaneously curbing the growth of GHG emissions.

- **Improper water utilization:** Improper water utilization refers to the wasteful use of water resources without achieving optimal results or benefits. In Uzbekistan, agriculture accounts for 90% of (World Bank, 2020) the entire water resources utilized (Figure 2). To be more precise, irrigating one hectare of cotton field in the country requires 10,000–11,000 cubic meters of water, whereas countries with comparable climates and landscapes use significantly less water, typically around 2-3 times less. This discrepancy underscores the importance of efficient water management practices and avoiding wastage, even while meeting agricultural needs (“Suvni tejash bo’yicha favqulodda ish tizimiga o’tiladi,” 2023). Uzbekistan is expected to maintain its high level of water stress unchanged until 2040 if current trends continue without significant intervention (World Resources Institute, 2013). The water industry receives an average annual allocation of \$1 billion, placing it as the fourth-highest recipient of budgetary funds after education, healthcare, and agriculture (“Suvni tejash bo’yicha favqulodda ish tizimiga o’tiladi,” 2023). Out of the total 4.3 million hectares of irrigated land in our country, approximately 30% have been equipped with water-saving technologies. In these specific clusters and farms, the adoption of such technologies has resulted in notable benefits: water savings of 30-40%, reductions in fertilizer and fuel usage by 25-30%, and an increase in overall productivity (“Suvni tejash bo’yicha favqulodda ish tizimiga

Figure 2: Annual freshwater withdrawals, agriculture (% of total freshwater withdrawal) in Uzbekistan.

Source: Food and Agriculture Organization, AQUASTAT data.

- Land degradation:** Based on the most recent data from the United Nations, more than 20% of the total land area in Central Asia is classified as degraded. This degradation encompasses approximately 80 million hectares, an expanse nearly four times the size of Kyrgyzstan. The impact extends to an estimated 30% of the combined population of the region (UNCCD, 2023). Although Uzbekistan exhibited the highest percentage of degraded land among Central Asian countries, it also experienced the most significant reduction, declining from 30% to 26% compared to 2015 levels. This improvement is noteworthy, despite the challenges posed by the drying of the Aral Sea, which has led to the degradation of approximately 3 million hectares of land in Uzbekistan. In response, Uzbekistan undertook extensive saxaul planting efforts between 2018 and 2022, covering an area of 1.6 million hectares. This initiative aims to mitigate salt and dust emissions originating from the desiccated Aral Sea bed (UNCCD, 2023). Uzbekistan farmers typically do not engage in active adoption of organic or conservation agriculture practices, which advocate for techniques such as crop rotations and minimum tillage while reducing reliance on chemical fertilizers, pesticides, plant growth regulators, and feed additives (Kodirxonov et al., 2022).

Current key actions for sustainable agriculture in Uzbekistan:

The global agrifood system faces the imperative of fulfilling multiple objectives such as ensuring food security, adapting to climate change, and substantially mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. In response to these challenges, the concept of Climate-smart Agriculture (CSA) has emerged as a comprehensive approach to achieving these goals while promoting sustainable development globally.

Like many other countries, Uzbekistan has also implemented various legislative measures aimed at environmental protection and the rational utilization of natural resources in agriculture since the 1990s. The country has undertaken consistent reforms focused on enhancing the efficient use of land and water resources, enhancing water and land management systems, and modernizing and expanding irrigation infrastructure.

Uzbekistan has set a target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) per GDP by 35% by 2030 from the 2010 level (UNDP climate promise, 2021), in line with its commitment to the Paris Agreement. This ambitious pledge necessitates efforts across all economic sectors, including agriculture. Furthermore, “New Uzbekistan” development Strategy for 2022–2026 outlines a goal of achieving a 5% annual growth rate in agriculture (“PF-60-сон 28.01.2022. 2022–2026-yillarga mo’ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to’g’risida,” 2022.). This growth target underscores the importance of enhancing agricultural productivity and sustainability while simultaneously reducing GHG emissions to meet Uzbekistan’s climate goals and promote economic development.

The Agriculture Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030 is a comprehensive national policy document designed to foster the sustainable development of the agri-food sector within the country’s economy

(“PF-5853-сон 23.10.2019. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020–2030-yillarga mo‘ljallangan strategiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida,” 2019). The overarching goal of this strategy is to implement policies that deepen ongoing reforms in the agricultural sector, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of the agri-food sector.

One of the priority areas of the strategy is Ensuring Rational Use of Natural Resources and Environmental Protection which focusses on implementing measures to promote sustainable land and water management practices, prevent soil degradation and erosion, conserve biodiversity, and mitigate the environmental impact of agricultural activities.

This policy brief recognizes that the transition to sustainable agriculture practices poses significant challenges and will require time and effort within the context of Uzbekistan. The agricultural system in the country is predominantly characterized by traditional approaches that prioritize intensive land and input utilization, primarily aimed at boosting productivity rather than preserving the environment. Research by Amirova underscores a deficiency in incentive mechanisms to encourage farmers to invest in solutions that enhance both productivity and sustainability. Designing advanced National Agri-food Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Program is already required by government (“PF-90-сон 10.06.2023. Ma‘muriy islohotlar doirasida qishloq xo‘jaligi VA oziq-ovqat sohasida davlat boshqaruvini samarali tashkil qilish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida,” 2023). Based on analysis, the program should include the following key areas while formulating:

- **Capacity Building:** Enhancing the capacity of farmers, extension services, and agricultural institutions in climate-smart agriculture practices, technologies, and decision-making is crucial for successful implementation of the program.
- **Water Management:** The program should prioritize strategies for improving water management practices, including irrigation efficiency, water conservation, and sustainable use of water resources.
- **Soil Health:** The program should include measures to promote soil conservation, restoration, and fertility enhancement through practices like conservation agriculture, agroforestry, and organic farming.

By addressing these issues comprehensively, a climate change agriculture program in Uzbekistan can contribute to building resilience, enhancing food security, and promoting sustainable development in the face of climate change challenges.

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Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta‘lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
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attestatsiya komissiyasi
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2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-
sonli qarori bilan ro‘yxatdan
o‘tkazilgan.